

A Survey of Indoor Air Quality Studies in the Philippines

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Abstract – Indoor air quality (IAQ) studies in the Philippines are relatively new especially as a field of research in universities. This paper presents a survey of IAQ studies and related research works done in academic institutions, industry and government institutions over the last seven years. These studies cover a quite wide range of topics which include: interior air quality studies of surface transportation done in air-conditioned urban buses, taxicabs, light rail transit, and ship cabins; indoor air quality investigation or air-conditioned spaces in institutional buildings such as libraries, laboratories, classrooms and cafeterias; and indoor air quality investigation of commercial buildings such as shopping malls, offices and entertainment spaces. Design of IAQ monitoring laboratory and measuring apparatus as well as air-conditioning equipment and system was also done.

In these studies, the contaminants investigated included chemical contaminants, biological contaminants and particulate matter. The assessment of biological contaminants was done by sedimentation test with the use of biostage impactor and tryptic soy agar as the medium. The medium was prepared in laboratory 2-3 days before sampling. The sampling apparatus was placed at various points of the air-conditioned space to be consistent with the protocol that was followed by different IAQ groups. The samples were placed inside an incubation chamber operating temperatures between 34.1 °C- 35.1 °C for 24 hours.

For the IAQ studies on surface transportation, it can be seen that for urban buses and ship cabins the determined level of concentration of biological contaminants is not acceptable. However, for taxicabs the percentage number of units with acceptable level of biological contaminants is much higher compared to the non-acceptable. For the LRT, the results show 50-50% acceptable and non-acceptable level of concentration. For both the institutional and commercial buildings considered in this survey, the levels of concentration of the biological contaminants are generally acceptable.

Over-all, the studies that have been done are a good start to pave the way to a more advanced and sophisticated study of airborne bacteria as they affect the quality of conditioned air which ultimately lead to a healthy and safe indoor environment.

Keywords – biological contaminants, chemical contaminants, indoor air quality

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper surveys research studies on indoor air quality and related ones done in the Philippines over the last seven years. With the exception of a few ones, all these studies have been completed as a required undergraduate thesis projects in the School of Mechanical Engineering of Mapua Institute of Technology and the Mechanical Engineering Department of De La Salle University-Manila. Others were done either as a research project of a faculty, a government agency staff or an individual hygienist.

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II. SUMMARY OF IAQ STUDIES

Over the last seven years, a number of indoor air quality studies have been conducted in various higher educational institutions, government agencies and private firms. In this paper, these studies will be limited to those done at the Mapua Institute of Technology, De La Salle University, Occupational Safety and Health Center, and Intel Technology Philippines, Inc. These studies may be divided into the following categories.

1. Interior Air Quality Studies of Surface Transportation
2. Investigation of IAQ of Institutional Buildings
3. Investigation of IAQ of Commercial Buildings
4. Instrumentation and Equipment/System Design to Promote Good IAQ.

A. Interior Air Quality Studies of Surface Transportation

Different studies have been conducted at the School of Mechanical Engineering and Mechanical Engineering Department of the Mapua Institute of Technology and De La Salle University, respectively pertaining to the interior air quality of air-conditioned surface transportation in Manila. These studies

aimed to assess the air quality of air-conditioned buses and recommend mechanical intervention to improve such quality.

These studies included the assessment of chemical and biological contaminants, particulate matter and volatile organic compounds (VOC's) present in air-conditioned urban buses. These contaminants pose health problems to the occupants of these vehicles such as respiratory ailments (colds, coughs, pneumonitis, asthma and allergic rhinitis), eye irritation and skin allergies.

These studies, which are in support of the Philippine Clean Air Act enacted to improve the quality of air in the environment, will make the bus passengers, drivers, conductors, and operators aware of the possible health hazards associated with the exposure to poor quality of air in air-conditioned surface transportation. These stakeholders are expected to take the necessary measures to reduce if not eliminate these hazards and consequently, enjoy a safe and healthy environment. The following completed studies at MIT and DLSU include:

- Assessment of Chemical Contaminants and Particulate Matter and Improvement of Air Quality in Air-Conditioned Urban Buses (Bosshard et al. 2003)
- Assessment of Chemical and Biological Contaminants and Improvement of Air Quality in Air-Conditioned Urban Buses (Austria et al. 2005)
- Installation of a Fan that Maintains Positive Pressure Inside an Air-Conditioned Urban Buses (Co et al. 2005)
- Assessment and improvement of Air Quality of Air-Conditioned Ship Cabins (Pua et al. 2006)
- Investigation of the Interior Air Quality of the Light Rail Transit Trains in Metro Manila (Correa et al. 2008)
- Investigation of the Interior Air Quality of Taxicabs Using LPG (Atienza et al. 2009)
- Investigation of the Interior of air Quality of Gasoline Taxicabs (Baldove et al. 2009)

B. Investigation of IAQ of Institutional Buildings

Investigation of the indoor quality of air-conditioned and non-air conditioned spaces in institutional buildings such as libraries, classrooms, laboratories and cafeteria was done. These studies determined the level of concentration of the chemical contaminants and particulate matter, specifically, the level of concentration of the carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, benzene and toluene. For the particulate matter, PM₁₀ was considered. In most of these studies, the concentration of biological contaminants was determined. The lists of these studies include the following:

- Investigation and Improvement of IAQ in Selected Grade School Classrooms (Dy et al. 2005)

- Assessment of Indoor Air Quality of De La Salle University-Manila Library Buildings (Belino 2005)
- Indoor Air Quality Investigation of Classrooms in Selected Grade Schools in Metro Manila (Belino 2007)
- Investigation of Biological Contaminants and Particulate Matter in Classrooms in Selected Grade School in Metro Manila (Sicat et al. 2009)
- Indoor Environment Quality Assessment of the Mapua Institute of Technology Library (Cain et al. 2009)
- Investigation and Recommendation on How to Improve the IAQ of North 401 Chemistry Laboratory of Mapua Institute of Technology (Gonzalez et al. 2009)

C. Investigation of IAQ of Commercial Buildings

Indoor air quality studies of air-conditioned spaces in commercial buildings such as shopping malls, offices and disco houses were undertaken. These studies assessed the concentration of chemical contaminants present in the space under consideration such as carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, benzene and toluene. For the particulate matter, PM₁₀ was considered. However, the biological contaminants were considered only in some of these studies. The list of studies includes the following:

- Assessment of Indoor Air Quality of Selected Shopping Malls in Metro Manila (Giron et al., 2008)
- Assessment of Indoor Air Quality of Intel Office Space Following Typhoon "Mileny" (Llanes, 2008)
- Assessment of Indoor Air Quality of an office Space (Aguilera, 2010)
- Fun and Hazards in Discos: A Case Study (OSHC)

III. DESIGN OF EQUIPMENT AND SYSTEM FOR IAQ

Aside from the assessment of contaminants present in air-conditioned spaces, IAQ research-related projects were also undertaken such as design of IAQ monitoring laboratory and measuring apparatus as well as air-conditioning equipment and system. While the level of concentration of carbon dioxide was monitored in most of these studies, not all possible chemical contaminants were considered. The determination of the level of concentration of biological contaminants was not also included. The lists of these studies include the following:

- Installation of a Wet Scrubber in an Air-conditioning Unit to Improve IAQ (De Castro et al. 2005)
- Development of an Efficient Intelligent Indoor Air Treatment System (Aganda et al. 2007)
- Development of an Indoor Environmental Quality Simulation Laboratory (Gonzalez et al. 2009)

IV. ASSESSMENT OF BIOLOGICAL CONTAMINANTS

The assessment of biological contaminants was done by sedimentation test with the use of biostage impactor and tryptic soy agar as the medium. The medium was prepared in laboratory 2-3 days before sampling. Tryptic Soy Agar could grow various

species of bacteria and fungi. The medium was placed in 90mm diameter Petri dish containing 20mL of water and 0.8 grams of agar mixture. The Petri dish, with the solution, was placed inside the biostage impactor. A pump was connected to the compactor with a fixed flow rate of 28.3 liter per minute and operated for about 30 minutes. The sampling apparatus was placed at various points of the air-conditioned space to be consistent with the protocol that was followed by different IAQ groups. The samples were placed inside an incubation chamber operating temperatures between 34.1 °C- 35.1 °C for 24 hours. The colonies that grew on the medium were counted and considered as colony forming units per plate (Cfu/plate). The number of colonies counted were corrected using positive hole correction factor. This was done to account for the possibility of multiple impactions of particles on a single hole. The equation is as follows:

$$\frac{CFU}{m^3} = \frac{\text{Colony Forming Unit}}{\text{Volume of Air}}$$

where

$$\text{Volume of air} = 28.3 \frac{L}{min} \times 30 \text{ mins} \times \frac{1m^3}{1000L}$$

The results of determining the biological contaminants in various studies mentioned in this paper are summarized in Table 1.

For the IAQ studies on surface transportation, it can be seen that for urban buses and ship cabins the determined level of concentration of biological contaminants is not acceptable. However, for taxicabs the percentage number of units with acceptable level of biological contaminants is much higher compared to the non-acceptable. For the LRT, the results show 50-50% acceptable and non- acceptable level of concentration. As observed in these studies, the maintenance and cleaning of these transportation systems have a direct bearing on the presence of the biological contaminants. However, factors such as personal hygiene of drivers, conductors, attendants and passengers as well as their number have increased the level of concentration of biological contaminants. For both the institutional and commercial buildings considered in this survey, the level of concentration of the biological contaminants is acceptable. Factors such as personal hygiene and number of the occupants had definitely affected the results. It could be deduced, however, the commercial buildings such as shopping malls and offices despite the volume of the occupants have lower concentration level of biological contaminants due to better maintenance and housekeeping of buildings as compared to institutional buildings.

Table I
SUMMARY OF CONCENTRATION OF BIOLOGICAL CONTAMINANTS IN SELECTED IAQ STUDIES IN THE PHILIPPINES

	RANGE OF VALUES (cfu/m ³)	AVERAGE VALUES	REMARKS (Raised on ACGIH Guideline)
Assessment of chemical and biological contaminants and improvement of air quality in air-conditioned urban buses.	3203 – 7977	5549	Not Acceptable
Assessment and improvement of air quality of air-conditioned ship cabins.	3354 – 5031	4388	Not Acceptable
Investigation of interior air quality of taxicabs using LPG.	524 – 1834	934	70% Acceptable (20 Taxis) 30% Not Acceptable
Investigation of the interior air quality of light rail transit trains in Metro Manila.	203 – 3565	1760	50% Acceptable 50% Not Acceptable
Investigation of the interior air quality of gasoline-power taxicabs.	105 – 1624	665	80% Acceptable (20 Taxis) 20% Not Acceptable
Indoor environment quality assessment of the Mapua Institute of Technology library.	486 – 2152	965	53% Acceptable (36 sampling points) 47% Not Acceptable
Investigation and recommendation on how to improve indoor air quality of north 401 Chemistry Laboratory of Mapua Institute of Technology.	72 – 398	232	Acceptable
Investigation of biological contaminants and particulate matter in classrooms of selected grade schools in Metro Manila.	426 – 1739	797	67% Acceptable 33% Not Acceptable
Assessment of the indoor air quality of selected shopping malls in Metro Manila.	372 – 2310	852	Generally Acceptable 79% Acceptable 21% Not Acceptable
Assessment of indoor air quality following typhoon "Milenyo".		Mean bacteria count 5.75 cfu/25 sq. cm. Mean mold count < 1 cfu/25 sq. cm.	Acceptable (based on Canadian Bioaerosol Guidelines)
Assessment of indoor air quality of an office space	50 – 700	290	Acceptable

V. CONCLUSION

Although a considerable number of indoor air quality studies have been undertaken in the Philippines over the last seven years, the assessment of contaminants was largely concentrated on the chemical contaminants and particulate matter. While the levels of concentration of biological contaminants are generally acceptable, much is still desired to improve the quality of air free from bacteria and fungi. The researches in these studies who are mostly mechanical engineers have to admit that they have almost zero background in microbiology as it is not included in their program of study. The short training that they get on procedures in biological contaminant sampling is still inadequate if a more serious study is to be undertaken in this regard. Furthermore, more sophisticated equipment and apparatus have to be procured to support such study. Overall, the studies that have been done are a good start to pave the way to a more advanced and sophisticated study of airborne bacteria as they affect the quality of conditioned air which ultimately lead to a healthy and safe indoor environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aguilera, N., et al. 2010. Investigation of the indoor air quality of an office space. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [2] Atienza, D.M., et al. 2009. Investigation of interior air quality of taxicabs using LPG. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [3] Austria, M.S., et al. 2005. Assessment of chemical and biological contaminants and improvement of air quality in air-conditioned urban buses. *Proc. Asia Pacific Conference on Built Environment. Manila Philippines*
- [4] Baldove, J.M.B., et al. 2009. Investigation of the interior air quality of gasoline-power taxicabs. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [5] Belino, Manuel C. 2005. Assessment of indoor air quality of De La Salle University – Manila Library Building. *Proc. Asia Pacific Conference on Built Environment. Manila, Philippines.*
- [6] Belino, Manuel C. 2007. Indoor air quality investigation of classrooms in selected grade schools in Metro Manila. *Proc. Asia Pacific Conference on Built Environment. Manila, Philippines.*
- [7] Cain, D.G.T., et al. 2009. Indoor environment quality assessment of the Mapua Institute of Technology library. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [8] Co, G. et al. 2005. Installation of a fan that maintains positive pressure inside an air-conditioned urban bus. *Proc. Asia Pacific Conference on Built Environment. Manila, Philippines.*
- [9] Correa, C.J.M., et al. 2009. Investigation of the interior air quality of light rail transit trains in Metro Manila. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [10] De Castro, M.R.H., et al. 2005. Installation of a wet scrubber in an air-conditioning unit to improve indoor air quality. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [11] Dy, A.L., et al. 2005. Investigation and improvement of indoor air quality in selected grade school classrooms. *Proc. Asia Pacific Conference on Built Environment. Manila, Philippines.*
- [12] Giron, D. et al. 2008. Assessment of the indoor air quality of selected shopping malls in Metro Manila. *Proc. 11th National Occupational Safety and Health Congress. Quezon City, Philippines.*
- [13] Gonzales, B.E.M., et al. 2009. Investigation and recommendation on how to improve indoor air quality of north 401 Chemistry Laboratory of Mapua Institute of Technology. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [14] Gonzales, K.A.M., et al. 2009. Development of an Indoor Environmental Quality Simulation Laboratory. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*
- [15] Llamas, J.L.M. 2008. Assessment of indoor air quality following typhoon “Milenyo”. *Proc. 11th National Occupational Safety and Health Congress. Quezon City, Philippines.*
- [16] Occupational Safety and Health Center of the Philippines. 2007. Fun and Hazards in Discos: A case study.
- [17] Pua, L., et al. 2006. Assessment and improvement of air quality of air-conditioned ship cabins. *De La Salle University undergraduate thesis.*
- [18] Sicat, G.K.B., et al. 2009. Investigation of biological contaminants and particulate matter in classrooms of selected grade schools in Metro Manila. *Mapua Institute of Technology undergraduate thesis.*